

17th Central European Lung Cancer Conference
including
Best of WCLC 2018

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Dear colleagues,

It is our pleasure to welcome you to the 17th Central European Lung Cancer Conference including Best of WCLC 2018. The Conference is organized by Institute for Pulmonary Diseases in Sremska Kamenica and Central European Lung Cancer Association – CELCA.

The aim of CELCC is to develop strategies for decreasing the burden of lung cancer in Europe. Therefore, we invite different specialists working in the field of lung cancer to participate at the CELCC 2018.

Thank you for your highly appreciated contribution to this Conference.

We wish you a pleasant and rewarding stay in Novi Sad!

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, sincerely,

Prof. Dr Ilija Andrijević
Conference President

Prof. Dr Nevena Secen
Conference President

Prof. Dr Robert Pirker
Member of the Board CELCA

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**APPLICATION OF THE 8TH REVISION OF TNM CLASSIFICATION OF LUNG
CARCINOMA**

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Introduction. In preparation for the 8th edition of the TNM classification for lung cancer the International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer (IASLC) analyzed 70,967 cases of non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). Analysis of the cases of NSCLC has allowed proposals for revisions to the T, N and M descriptors and TNM Stage groupings.

Goal. To present result of pTNM classification at Institute for pulmonary diseases of Vojvodina in one-year period.

Material and methods. All patients diagnosed and operated with NSCLC in one year period were included in this study. Exclusion criteria were incomplete resection and primary tumor resection without lymph node resection.

Results. From 185 patients, 57 (31%) were females and 128 (69%) were males, aged from 26 to 82 years (average 62 yrs ($\pm 7,7$)). Pathohistological diagnosis revealed adenocarcinoma in 46%, squamous cell carcinoma in 42%, large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma (LCNEC) in 6%, while other types of carcinoma were diagnosed in 6% of patients. Size of the tumor ranged from 1 cm to 10,5 cm. In 64 patients we found lymph node metastasis, of which 47 (73,4%) had N1, and 17 (26,6%) N2 stage of the disease. Invasion of visceral pleura was found in 28 (15%) patients, type PL1 in 71,4% and PL type 2 in 28,6%. After applying 8th revision of TNM, in 48,65% (90) of patients TNM stage has changed.

Conclusion. Multi-disciplinary approach and the close cooperation among medical and radiation oncologists, pulmonologists, surgeons, radiologists and pathologists is important in properly staging of lung cancer as well as, in treatment plans.

Key words: lung carcinoma, TNM classification, diagnosis